

DESIGN OF PASSIVE MORPHING WING STRUCTURES USING ELASTIC INSTABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

The study of elastic instabilities, i.e. buckling, in lightweight structures is a fundamental design aspect. For the structural elements involved, local buckling results in a modified load path and a change of the effective stiffness. These effects can be tolerated under certain conditions, in particular, if the structure retains its load-carrying capacity. This investigation exploits the design of structures undergoing local buckling to realise novel functionalities of structural components in addition to their load carrying function. In particular, the utilisation of structurally tailored buckling elements is presented for aeroelastically aided shape adaptation of lift generating lightweight systems. This concept is applied to a simplified wing box structure with one spar designed as the buckling component. The onset of instability causes the torsional stiffness of the structure to change and the shear centre to relocate while not influencing the bending characteristics significantly. As a result, the bending-twisting coupling of the wing box is designed to enable a desired twisting resulting in morphing to be obtained only by the action of external forces. Hence, the aerodynamic loading defines the onset and development of buckling making this morphing mechanism purely passive. Our investigations demonstrate that inducing local instabilities in a carefully tailored compliant spar allows for obtaining the desired deformation of the wing structure enabling simple shape adaptation. This concept is extended to the design of a wing structure featuring a NACA0012 profile and a wing box comprised by two spars under realistic loading conditions. It is shown that compliant systems with strategically positioned components of variable stiffness arising from elastic instabilities offer the potential of reducing structural complexity and actuation requirements, while providing global morphing due to a change in effective stiffnesses of the structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Static instabilities are a well-known phenomenon in lightweight design [1][2]. The effects resulting from local buckling including the change in shape of the involved structural elements and the modified load path commonly are considered a drawback [3][4]. However, design techniques that tolerate local buckling can be structurally beneficial in certain applications providing overall system performance after the onset of instability [5][6][7]. In fact, there is a current trend in research to utilise local instabilities as a design parameter to realise novel functionalities of structural components [8][9][10].

One up to now unexplored field of exploiting the effects resulting from static instabilities is shape adaptation of compliant structures like wings. For such lightweight systems, the control of the bending-twisting coupling is of particular interest and has been studied through several approaches [11][12]. For a wing box model comprised by two spars, Raither et. al. introduced a semi-active control technique of the bending-twisting coupling. By varying the elastic moduli of one web utilizing smart materials with adjustable shear stiffness, the shear centre location and torsional stiffness of the structure is changed actively resulting in a controllable twist [11][13].

The objective of this investigation is to study the utilisation of elastic instabilities for the bending-twisting deformation mechanism for applications in morphing. In this approach, the torsional stiffness and location of the shear centre of a structure are influenced passively by designing structural components in which instability occurs in a deliberate way. For that purpose, a structural tailoring

procedure providing a particular material anisotropy by varying fibre orientation and thickness of the component is introduced.

Figure 1 shows the methodology of adjusting torsional stiffness and shear centre location of wing structures for a simplified wing model considering only the load carrying wing box. One web of the structure (thickness t_w) is designed as the buckling component.

Figure 1- a) Wing box model with web designed to buckle b) Cross section before onset of buckling c) Cross Section after Buckling. Relocation of shear center (S.C.) due to instability results in buckling induced twisting of the structure

For the applied loading shown in Fig. 1, the structure twists as the shear centre (S.C.) does not lie in the axis of load application (Fig. 1 b)). At the occurrence of local instability the shear centre of the structure moves along the x -axis. Furthermore, the torsional stiffness of the structure is changed while the bending stiffness remains largely unaffected. These effects result in an additional twist induced passively by the local instability of the web (Fig. 1 c)).

To estimate the effect of buckling on the overall twist of the thin-walled beam, the buckling web is isolated to analyse its postbuckling behaviour under representative loading and boundary conditions. The reduction in shear stiffness due to the development of diagonal tension fields is captured by defining equivalent shear moduli corresponding to buckled sections for the given design and loading. Applying these results to the simplified wing box model, the twisting due to the instability is calculated analytically. The results are compared to numerical postbuckling calculations conducted with the commercial finite element code ABAQUS[®] Standard/FEA.

The deformation mechanism exploiting buckling-induced twisting is applied for aeroelastically aided shape adaptation of wings. The wing structure features a NACA0012 profile and a wing box comprised by two spars. The front spar is designed as the buckling component undergoing instability at a prescribed load level. The wing model is loaded under realistic conditions applying a pressure field derived by the open source software XFOIL [14]. A numerical linear buckling analysis provides buckling coefficients and identifies the mode shape of the spar as the instability is triggered. For a preliminary wing design, the change in angle of attack due to buckling is calculated. A discussion about the applicability of the proposed concept to wing structures concludes this investigation.

2 ANALYTICAL COMPOSITE BEAM MODEL

The study of utilising elastic instabilities for influencing the twisting of wing structures is introduced for a simplified wing model. This approach only considers the load carrying wing box comprised by two flanges and two spars (Fig. 1). The investigation addresses the analytical prediction of the twisting of hollow composite beams with rectangular cross section considering the effects resulting from local buckling.

The material utilised is unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) with the material data given in Table 1. The buckling spar is designed by layers with identical fibre orientation β to the main axis of the beam (Fig. 1). The lay-up of the remaining components is designed symmetrically and balanced. The boundary conditions are fixed at all edges at the root and free at all other locations. The loading is simplified by applying equidistant distributed concentrated forces acting in y -direction (Fig.1). For the given conditions, the lateral shear force is constant in beam regions located between load introduction points. If the shear centre of a section does not lie in the axis of load application, this results in a section-wise constant torsional moment acting on the beam. For free warping, the twisting of the beam is described by the de Saint-Venant torsion theory:

Property	Symbol	Units	CFRP-UD
Young's Modulus 0°	E_1	[GPa]	135
Young's Modulus 90°	E_2	[GPa]	10
In-plane Shear Modulus	G_{12}	[GPa]	5
Major Poisson's ratio	ν_{12}	[-]	0.3
Tensile Strength 0°	X_t	[MPa]	1500
Compressive Strength 0°	X_c	[MPa]	1200
Tensile Strength 90°	Y_t	[MPa]	50
Compressive Strength 90°	Y_c	[MPa]	250
In-plane Shear Strength	S	[MPa]	70

Table 1: Material data [15]

$$\vartheta(x) = \frac{M_t(x)}{4A_0^2} \oint \frac{ds}{G(s)t(s)} \quad (1)$$

where A_0 is the enclosed area by the circumference of the section, t the thickness, G the shear modulus, M_t the torsional moment and s the control variable in circumferential direction.

The lay-ups of the flanges and the left web are identical (thickness t_C , shear modulus G_C). The web designed to buckle has a smaller thickness t_{Web} and a shear modulus G_{Web} depending on the chosen fibre orientation β . In order to calculate the shear modulus G_{Web} before the onset of buckling, this component is isolated from the wing box structure. Under the assumption that the web is restrained in x -direction by the flanges due to their significantly higher thickness, the shear modulus of the web G_{web} can be calculated by the set of equations describing the stress strain relation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{xx} \\ 0 \\ \tau_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{Q}_{11} & \hat{Q}_{12} & \hat{Q}_{16} \\ \hat{Q}_{21} & \hat{Q}_{22} & \hat{Q}_{26} \\ \hat{Q}_{61} & \hat{Q}_{62} & \hat{Q}_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \varepsilon_{yy} \\ \gamma_{xy} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

with Q_{ij} representing the coefficients of the lamina stiffness matrix [16]. The twisting of the beam can be calculated with Equation 1 as all shear moduli of webs and flanges are known.

Instability of the web leads to the development of a diagonal tension field. Hence the load path and effective stiffness of the web undergoing buckling change. In order to permit the utilisation of the de Saint-Venant torsion theory also in this case, the actual shearing response of the web undergoing instability must be assigned to this section of the beam. Hence an equivalent shear modulus G_{eq} is defined. This equivalent property takes the effects resulting from postbuckling into account. The twist at a certain position x of the buckled beam can be calculated with

$$\vartheta_B(x) = \frac{M_t(x)}{4A_0^2} \oint \frac{ds}{G(s,x)t(s)} = \frac{M_t(x)}{4A_0^2} \sum \frac{\Delta s}{G_{eq}(x)t(s)} \quad (3)$$

assuming that the equivalent shear modulus G_{eq} is constant over the height of the buckling web. Integration of the individual section twists along the beam allows for calculating the twist angle at any position of the beam.

3 STRUCTURAL TAILORING OF BUCKLING SPAR

The structural tailoring process of the buckling spar aims at triggering the onset of instability and exploiting the reduction in shear stiffness occurring during postbuckling in a beneficial way. The objective of this study is to obtain the buckling coefficient and the equivalent shear modulus G_{eq} for the beam model shown in Figure 1. For that purpose the web designed to undergo instability is isolated applying simplified boundary conditions to capture the effects resulting from the connection to the flanges. Figure 2 shows the isolated web with applied boundary conditions. The plate is fixed at $x = 0$ and free at $x = L$ while being restrained in x -direction at the flange connections, hence $\varepsilon_{xx} = 0$ at $y = \pm H/2$. Furthermore, the out of plane deformation U_z at all edges is restrained. Figure 2 shows

the buckling coefficients obtained by a numerical eigenvalue analysis conducted with the commercial finite element code ABAQUS[®] Standard/FEA. The web is designed as a carbon fibre composite plate ($L = 1m, H = 0.04m$) with the material data shown in Table 1 and a thickness of $t = 0.25$ mm. The study considers two load cases. For application in the simplified beam model, the plate is loaded with a concentrated force $F = 100N$ acting in y -direction at point $y = +H/2$ and $x = L$ such that a constant shear load exists at all positions. This load case is compared to a line load $f = 100N/m$ acting in y -direction at the edge $y = +H/2$ representing more accurately the load acting at a spar of a wing structure under aerodynamic pressure. Both load cases lead to comparable results for the buckling coefficients which are utilised to tailor the onset of buckling of the web.

Two zones of interest in Figure 2 can be observed, the first at fibre angles in the range $[-20^\circ \dots 0^\circ]$ (in the following referred to as zone A) and the second at fibre angles in the range $[20^\circ \dots 70^\circ]$ (in the following referred to as zone B). The advantage of the first zone is that the global minimum of buckling coefficients is reached. For a given load, the onset of buckling occurs first for plates designed with fibre angles of this region. Hence the effects resulting from postbuckling are mostly pronounced. The advantage of the second zone is the wide span of fibre angles in which the buckling coefficients do not change significantly.

Figure 2 - Buckling coefficients for a unidirectional composite plate under line loading with fixed free boundary conditions for two different load cases

For the calculation of the equivalent shear modulus of the buckled plate, the reduction of shear stiffness in the postbuckling regime after the onset of buckling must be calculated. Hence, a nonlinear postbuckling analysis for the simplified plate model introduced in this section is conducted (Fig. 2). Geometrical imperfections are imposed into the initial model by superposition of the first eigenmodes obtained by a linear buckling analysis. As the change in shear stiffness does not only depend on the fibre angle but also on the nominal shear force applied, the load ratio

$$\xi = \frac{\tau}{\tau_{\text{crit}}} \quad (4)$$

is introduced [17]. This factor relates the nominal shear loading τ to the critical loading τ_{crit} under which buckling occurs for a plate with fibre angle β .

The buckling coefficient, and hence the load at the onset of buckling, is highly dependent on the degree of anisotropy (Fig. 2). For that reason the shear stiffness after the onset of instability is related to the initial shear stiffness of the plate with fibre angle β . The shear stiffness reduction

$$\chi = \frac{G_{eq}}{G_{initial}} \quad (5)$$

relates the equivalent shear stiffness G_{eq} to the initial shear stiffness $G_{initial}$ of the composite plate before buckling occurs [17]. For maximising the effect on the global system response due to the instability of the web, not the absolute value of the shear stiffness, but the degree and development of the shear stiffness reduction is of importance.

Figure 3 shows the relative shear stiffness reduction as a function of the load ratio ξ and the fibre angle β . Two fibre directions representing zones A and B of low buckling coefficients (Fig. 2) are compared. For each simulation, the development of the shear stiffness reduction is calculated until the nominal load reaches four times the buckling load ($\xi = 4$). Due to the low buckling coefficient of a plate of zone A, instability occurs at the smallest nominal load. The load ratio $\xi = 4$ is reached before instability is triggered for the plate of zone B with $\beta = 25^\circ$. The results are compared to an isotropic plate made of aluminium that is utilised for the estimation of the effect of anisotropy. For fibre direction $\beta = -10^\circ$, the relative reduction is $\chi = 44\%$. A greater reduction in shear stiffness is reached for the isotropic case and for a fibre orientation of $\beta = 25^\circ$. It can be observed that the reduction in shear stiffness for plates of zone A is lower compared to plates from zone B. For $\beta = 25^\circ$, not only the maximum reduction of shear stiffness is the greatest with $\chi = 10\%$, but also the gradient of the reduction for low load ratios ξ is greatest (Fig. 4). Hence this fibre angle is chosen for the design of the buckling web of the simplified beam model for the proof of concept of buckling-induced twisting.

Figure 3- Relative reduction in shear modulus as a function of relative shear load

Figure 4 - Relative reduction in shear modulus as a function of fibre angle

4 ANALYTICAL AND NUMERICAL MODEL FOR BUCKLING-INDUCED TWISTING

In the previous section the shear stiffness reduction χ of a composite plate has been calculated for a specific load case and boundary conditions to model a web undergoing buckling of the simplified beam model analytically. With these results, the equivalent shear moduli of a buckled section with given fibre angle β and load ratio ξ can be calculated

$$G_{eq} = \chi G_{initial} = f(\beta, \xi) \cdot G_{initial}. \quad (6)$$

For the simplified model of a beam loaded by concentrated forces, the nominal shear stress τ is constant in the sections between the load introduction points. Hence, for a given fibre angle, the equivalent shear moduli G_{eq} are assigned to each buckled section. Figure 5 shows the simplified beam model with sections that have been assigned a certain value of equivalent shear modulus G_{eq} due to the known loading and fibre direction.

Figure 5 –Beam models for calculation of buckling induced torsion. a) Simplified beam model for analytical solution b) Finite element model with composite box section (blue), buckling web (grey) and ribs (red)

For a beam with length $L = 1 \text{ m}$ and a square cross section ($H = W = 0.05 \text{ m}$), the twisting angle ϕ about the x -axis is calculated with Equation 3 which describes the twisting $\vartheta(x)$ of each section:

$$\phi(x) = \int_0^x \vartheta(x) d\hat{x}. \quad (7)$$

Note that the constant moment $M(x)$ in regions between load introduction points causes the twisting to be constant. Hence the twisting angle $\phi(x)$ changes linearly within these sections.

Figure 6 shows the comparison of the twisting angles $\vartheta(x)$ for the analytical and numerical solution. The lay-up of the composite wing box section is $[4x 0^\circ 4x 90^\circ]_{sym}$ and the thickness results as $t_{Box} = 2 \text{ mm}$. The lay-up of the web designed to buckle is $[25^\circ 25^\circ]$ (thickness $t_{Web} = 0.25 \text{ mm}$). The load is applied at eight locations such that before instability is triggered the load introduction points coincide with the shear centre of the section. Hence prior to buckling no twisting occurs. The torsion is purely induced by the instability. For the given geometry and loading the total buckling force is approximately $F_{crit,tot} = 400 \text{ N}$ resulting in $F_{crit,i} = 50 \text{ N}$ for each concentrated force. Figure 6 a) compares twisting at the tip $\vartheta(x = L)$ for the analytical and numerical solution. The finite element beam model does not have ribs except of one rib at the tip where the twisting is measured. The analytical calculation of the twist of the beam enables a fast approach to estimate the effects of local instability on the global structural response and shows a good agreement to the analytical solution.

Figure 6 b) shows the twisting angle $\phi(x)$ as a function of the length of a beam with ribs distributed along its length where the twisting angle is measured. The twisting angle $\phi(x)$ is section wise linear both for the analytical and numerical solution. The significant difference in the results of the solutions is explained by the fact that the change in shear stiffness leading to the torsion is calculated for plate models which are not restrained to deform along the y -axis shown in Figure 5. As the ribs significantly contribute to the stiffness of the flanges to deform, the buckling cannot develop

in the similar manner as it does for the unrestrained case. Hence the change in shear stiffness is lower than predicted by the analytical model resulting in a smaller twisting of the beam.

Figure 6 - Comparison of analytical and numerical solutions a) Tip twisting (Fe model without ribs) b) Twisting angles for beam model (FE model with ribs)

5 WING DESIGN

5.1 Numerical model

The application of the concept of achieving passive global shape adaptation by locally introducing instabilities is extended to a wing structure featuring a NACA 0012 profile and a wing box comprised by two spars. The front spar is designed as the buckling component. Figure 7 shows the finite element model of the wing.

Figure 7 - Wing model. Wing structure comprised by wing box flanges (red), front and rear spar (blue), front section and rear section (grey) and ribs (green)

Assuming incompressible and inviscid flow over the airfoil section, the pressure distribution for a given flow velocity v and initial angle of attack α is calculated utilising the software XFOIL [14]. First, a numerical static eigenvalue analysis is conducted utilising a linear perturbation method on a finite element model of the wing utilising the commercial finite element code ABAQUS[®] Standard/FEA. This analysis serves to calculate the buckling coefficients of the wing spar and to determine the shape functions of the buckling modes. Furthermore, this analysis identifies further buckling regions of the wing structure. For the postbuckling simulation, geometric imperfections are imposed into the initial geometry of the wing structure by superposition of the shape functions

obtained in the linear buckling analysis. The nonlinear postbuckling analysis is conducted with a static solution procedure utilising automatic stabilization [18]. Both for the linear and nonlinear analysis shell elements with reduced integration have been utilised. For all simulations presented in this report, the applicability of these elements compared to geometrically quadratic and fully integrated elements is reviewed and a mesh convergence study has been conducted. To estimate the effect of the buckling spar on the overall shape deformation of the wing structure, a static analysis of the same model is conducted not taking geometrical nonlinearities into account. The result of this simulation is the twisting of the wing structure without buckling and is compared to the results obtained from a realistic nonlinear postbuckling analysis.

5.2 Preliminary Design Study

For the initial design, the wing box comprised by two flanges and the rear spar is designed with plies of unidirectional carbon fibre composite with material data shown in Table 1. With a ply thickness of $t_{\text{ply}} = 0.125\text{mm}$ and the stacking sequence of $[4x 0^\circ 4x 90^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$ the lay-up is balanced and symmetric and has a total thickness of $t_{\text{Box}} = 2.0\text{mm}$. The front and rear section are designed by the same material with a stacking sequence $[0^\circ 90^\circ]_{\text{sym}}$ and a total thickness of $t_{\text{FR}} = 0.5\text{mm}$. The ribs are made of aluminium (thickness $t_{\text{Rib}} = 0.5\text{mm}$). The length of the wing structure is $L = 1.3\text{m}$ and the chord is $c = 0.3\text{m}$ (Figure 7). Table 2 shows the wing dimensions. The wing is fixed at all nodes at the root ($x = 0$) and free to deform at all other locations.

Dimension	Symbol	Units	Value
Thickness Wing Box	t_{Box}	mm	2
Thickness Front Part	t_{FR}	mm	0.5
Thickness Rear Part	t_{FR}	mm	0.5
Thickness Buckling Web	t_{Web}	mm	0.18
Thickness Ribs	t_{Rib}	mm	0.5
Wing span	L	m	1.3
Wing chord	c	m	0.3
Front spar position	$z_{\text{spar},1}$	m	$0.25 \cdot c$
Rear spar position	$z_{\text{spar},2}$	m	$0.60 \cdot c$

Table 2: Dimensions for preliminary design

Figure 8 shows the results of an initial wing concept for the design proposed in this section. The buckling wing spar has a fibre orientation of $\beta = 25^\circ$ and thickness $t = 0.18\text{mm}$. The initial angle of attack of the wing is $\alpha = 5^\circ$ at a flow velocity of $v = 42.75\text{m/s}$. Due to the linear decreasing shearing load from the root to the tip, buckling first occurs close to the root and develops in direction of the tip when the load is further increased. Figure 8 shows both final angles of attack for a linear and nonlinear analysis. It can be observed, that the softening of the front spar due to the instability and the development of a diagonal tension field leads to a shifting of the shear centre in direction to the rear part of the wing. This leads to an augmentation of the angle of attack passively achieved by the occurrence of instability at the front spar.

For the failure analysis, the maximum stress criterion, the Tsai-Wu criterion and the Tsai-Hill criterion are utilized [19]. The area of critical loading for a wing structure with geometry and loading described in Section 5.1 is investigated. All criteria result in comparable failure indices which is caused by the fact that one ratio of stress component to its maximal allowable value is significantly higher than the ratios for the other stress components. For the unidirectional lay-up, high failure indices occur close to the root due to the buckling-induced bending of the web. The tensile stress resulting from bending – occurring in direction of the compression part of the diagonal tension field – is critical due to the very low tensile strength in transverse fibre direction (Table 1).

Due to the great amount of parameters influencing the occurrence of instability and the resulting change in twist of the wing structure, the possibility of structural tailoring of the buckling component and the wing design is utilized to enhance the morphing effect. For a spar design that is tailored in thickness such that buckling occurs not only at the root, but simultaneously at four equidistant

positions, Figure 9 shows the comparison of the twisting angles as a function of the span position. It can be seen in that the twisting of the structure that is not induced by instability is comparable to the one shown in Figure 8. However, due to the structural tailoring procedure of the spar, the buckling-induced torsion could be significantly enhanced. Furthermore, the failure indices could be reduced such that no failure occurs for the given loading.

Figure 8 - Preliminary design. Change in angle of attack for linear and nonlinear wing analysis. Nonlinear analysis considers buckling of front spar.

Figure 9 – Improved design. Change in angle of attack for linear and nonlinear wing analysis Nonlinear analysis considers buckling of front spar.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This investigation presents a concept of utilising local instabilities for passive shape adaptation of wing structures. The proof of concept is shown for a simplified rectangular wing box model comprised by two flanges and two spars (Fig. 1). One spar is designed as the buckling component undergoing instability at a prescribed load level. When instability is triggered in the spar, a diagonal tension field develops changing the load path and directional stiffnesses of this component. These effects influence the torsional stiffness and the shear centre location of the wing box and result in a buckling-induced twisting of the section. Morphing is achieved purely passive by exploiting the external aerodynamic loading without the need of additional actuators.

Structural tailoring of the unidirectional composite spar for a particular material anisotropy enables to achieve a desired onset of buckling and reduction in shear stiffness in the postbuckling regime. For that purpose, the buckling web is isolated and analysed to its postbuckling behaviour under representative loading and boundary conditions. The definition of an equivalent shear modulus corresponding to a buckled region of the wing box enables to calculate the buckling-induced twisting of the wing box by means of simple analytical approaches. These results are compared to nonlinear numerical simulations taking the instability of the spar into account.

For the proposed design, the effects resulting from buckling mainly depend on the fibre angle of the buckling component and the applied load. By further increasing the load after the onset of buckling, the shear stiffness reduction continues due to the development of a diagonal tension field. For an applied load twice, thrice and four-times greater than the buckling load, the torsional stiffness of the wing box decreases by approximately 50%, 70% and 80%, respectively. This effect and the shear centre relocation result in a twisting of the wing box. Twist angles up to three degrees can be achieved passively for the range of loading levels and the structural arrangement presented for the simplified wing box.

This concept is extended to achieve aeroelastically aided shape adaptation of compliant wing structures. The considered wing features a NACA0012 profile and a wing box comprised by two spars. The front spar is the buckling component undergoing instability at a prescribed load level. The buckling-induced torsion of the wing is compared to a linear analysis not taking instability into account. Due to the increase in torsional stiffness of a wing structure compared to a structure only considering the wing box, the level of buckling-induced twisting is less pronounced. Hence, successful implementation of this morphing mechanism must aim for comparatively torsion compliant front and rear sections of the wing.

Several challenges still remain to be addressed before the presented concept can be implemented. The bending of the buckling spar due to the development of the diagonal tension field leads to high tensile stresses occurring in transverse fibre direction. As the strength of the material is very low in this direction, provisions must be taken to reduce the loading in this direction. One possible approach is to design the spar with a reinforcing layer. In order to augment the buckling-induced twisting of the wing structure, the tailoring of the spar needs to take the possibility of different fibre orientations and spar thicknesses in span direction into account. Applying the proposed improvements, the passive shape adaptation mechanism presented in this paper can be extended from the simplified model to a realistic wing structure offering the possibility to reduce weight and complexity of lift generating structures like wings or rotor blades.

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